

STU
MTF

SLOVAK UNIVERSITY OF
TECHNOLOGY IN BRATISLAVA
FACULTY OF MATERIALS SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY IN TRNAVA

*The aim of the Faculty of Materials Science and Technology of the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava is to create and enact a culture at the institutional level that supports **gender synergy** in order to create a **balanced research environment**.*

Gender Equality Status Analysis

An extensive assessment of **gender bias** and **inequalities** both inside the Institution and in the external Innovation Ecosystem where it is positioned.

This research has been carried out by MTF - STU BA in the context of CALIPER project through the funded European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 873134.

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

The internal assessment followed the **three ERA priorities on Gender Equality*** and examined them in the context of **specific activity/service areas** inside MTF - STU BA through the collection of qualitative and quantitative data.

The data collection was conducted by the institution researchers, through **desk research, policy analysis, interviews, surveys and focus groups**.

Key Findings

HUMAN RESOURCES

Institution recruitment and hiring processes **do not follow officially established gender-sensitive protocols**.

During recent years, **more female than male candidates** have been interviewed for **administrative and technical positions**, while the opposite occurred for the academic ones.

The current academic staff is almost exclusively composed of **male professors**, while **senior lecturers are mainly female**.

22 male professors > 1 female professor

39 senior male lecturers < 47 female senior lecturers

*Council of the European Union (2015). Conclusions on advancing Gender Equality in the European Research Area. RECH 295, COMPET 551, SOC 703

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

The Institution has not adopted processes to identify female talents and provide talented young women with career development and/or mentoring programmes yet

MTF - STU BA applies measurements to improve work-life balance, mobility of researchers, decision making and transparency. Although, according to the results of the study, employees seem not to be sufficiently aware of the existing policies, which indicates the need for further institutional awareness activities.

INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE

The institutional governance does not include specific measures or bodies targeting on gender equality, such as Gender Equality Plans, Gender Equality Bodies, activities for empowering women to apply for leadership positions, or others.

The decision-making bodies such as the management of the faculty, the scientific board, the academic senate and leadership positions are covered mainly by males.

Gendered Composition of decision making bodies

Faculty Management		Scientific Board	
83%	17%	96%	4%
Men	Women	Men	Women
Academic Senate		Leadership Positions	
70%	30%	60%	40%
Men	Women	Men	Women

Status of Gender Equality inside the Institution

External and internal institutional communications activities do not appear to be gender-sensitive. However, the creation of communication materials does not follow relative gender-sensitive communication policies.

RESEARCH & TEACHING

Currently, the Institution does not allocate funds for specific programs on gender studies and guidelines and/or policies on integrating gender analysis into research are not in place.

Concerning teaching, **official guidelines to integrate the gender dimension do not exist** in MTF - STU BA. Nevertheless, no gender bias in teaching were identified during the study.

STUDENT SERVICES

MTF - STU BA has a **relatively high number of female students** who enrol in STEM studies, **but only half of them graduate.** Most of those who do it continue to postgraduate studies, but **only a few of them continue their career to PhD studies.**

During the recent years, the percentage of female students enrolled in STEM studies has documented a minor decrease..

2019: 461 Female students enrolled - 25%

2018: 517 Female students enrolled- 27%

2017: 614 Female students enrolled - 27%

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TRANSFER TO MARKET

Throughout 2017 and 2018 35% female and 65% male researchers were involved in **joint research projects with companies**, while in 2019 the gender ratio gap changed to **40% females and 60% males**.

Share of researches involved in joint projects

However, the **gender ratio of patenting researchers is majorly imbalanced** with men covering the with 80%.

INTERSECTIONALITY

Intersectionality is **not included as a component of equality policies** within the Institution. The MTF - STU BA **has not developed any measures and/or guidelines** to adopt an intersectional approach or to raise awareness among the staff and students on the concept of intersectionality, **yet**.

The complete report is publicly available [here](#)

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Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

The first part of the external assessment included an analysis of the **national legal and policy framework**. The second, focused on the **National and Regional Innovation Ecosystems**. A **context analysis** was implemented through a dedicated desk research and complemented with interviews with internal stakeholders. In addition to the context analysis, a **mapping** was conducted by MTF - STU BA to identify existing and potential synergies with external stakeholders. The mapping included a focus group with internal stakeholders, a survey for external stakeholders and a Social Network Analysis.

Key Findings

NATIONAL LEGAL AND POLICY FRAMEWORK

In the Slovak Republic, **the principle of equal treatment** and the prohibition of discrimination based on sex, gender or other status are addressed at **national level**.

Hence, women and men have the right to equal treatment as regards **access to employment, pay, and promotion, vocational training, and working conditions**.

However, no specific provisions are foreseen for what concerns the area of Higher Education and/or Scientific Research & Innovation.

The approval of the new "**National Strategy for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic**" and the new "**Action Plan for Gender Equality in the Slovak Republic**" is still pending for the next period.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

There is **notable imbalance** concerning STEM higher education students and researchers, as the female share is around the 30% in both cases.

STEM High School Students ratio **STEM Researchers ratio**

Despite being higher than the EU average, the evolution of **employment rate in Research and Innovation** has registered a decrease of the female share in the 2014-2018 time frame (**from the 42,49% to 40,79%**).

Women funders of start-ups and leaders of innovative enterprises are a minority in contrast to men.

The **integration of gender as a scientific research dimension** only happens at the moment **through dedicated projects** funded at national level and research activities, but **an overall strategy is still missing**.

Status of Gender Equality in the Innovation Ecosystem

SOCIAL NETWORK ANALYSIS

The Analysis resulted with the identification of **33 external stakeholders**, the majority of them belonging to the "Academia and Universities" sector.

Overall, **24 collaborations are led by women (representing 72% of the total)** on the side of MTF - STU BA. Such collaborations mainly concern the implementation of specific research projects.

The majority of the collaborations led by women are held with Academia & Universities. It is, also, notable that **all of the Institution's identified collaborations with Industry & Business stakeholders are led by women.**

Gender equality is only taken into account in only one project related to the involvement of girls between 12 and 15 years old into STEM subjects and their enrollment in STEM school.

The complete report is publicly available [here](#)

This research has been conducted in the context of Horizon 2020 project, CALIPER.

The results will be used for the project's next implementation phases.

MTF - STU BA is one of the 9 Research Organisations across Europe which participates in CALIPER to develop a **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)** and engage the local Innovation Hubs to transfer the gained knowledge beyond academia.

Discover more about CALIPER

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